

The Effect of Information Technology, Digital Transformation, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance in Regional Office the National Land Agency

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Abstract:- By using work satisfaction as a mediating variable among employees of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province, this study seeks to understand how information technology and digital transformation affect employee performance. Associative quantitative research techniques are being used. responders included 197 workers at the BPN's regional office in the NTB Province. Questionnaire-based data collecting methods. In this study, smart PLS 3.2.7 software was utilized for the data analysis process. The statistical test findings reveal that while digital transformation has a favorable and considerable impact on performance, information technology has no discernible impact on worker output. A favorable and considerable impact on job satisfaction is also provided by information technology and the digital revolution. The job satisfaction variable, which has a favorable and large impact on employee performance, demonstrates the same thing. In the findings of the mediation test, work satisfaction is possible to significantly and positively mediate the impact of information technology and digital transformation on employee performance at the Regional Office of BPN NTB Province.

Keywords:- Information Technology, Digital Transformation, Employee Performance, and Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important basic capital in an organization, institution, or agency. The importance of human resources is not something that is a new awareness of humans (Alamsyah, et al, 2019). Therefore, in order to support organizational goals, of course, it must be supported by the quality of human resource performance. A good organization must be supported by good employee performance as well (Antasari & Sukartha, 2015). Magnier-Watanabe et al. (2020) say that employee performance is the result of the implementation of tasks and activities carried out.

Based on data from the Performance Report of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, there are arrears of land services up to 2022 in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, seen from the comparison of the withdrawal of statistical data as of December 31, 2021 and the withdrawal of statistical data as of December 31, 2022 for service arrears up to 2021. Statistical data as of December 31, 2021 shows that service arrears are 12,146 files, while statistical data as of December 31, 2022 shows service arrears of 4,980 files. This shows that in 2022 there has been a settlement of 7,166 files or 53.25% of the total arrears, which can be seen in the table below.

Table 1 Arrears of Work within the NTB Provincial BPN Regional Office until December 31, 2022

No	Work Unit (Land Office)	Number of Delinquent Files until 2021	Number of Delinquent Files until 2022	Arrears Settlement	%
1	Kanwil BPN Provinsi NTB	18	16	2	11,11
2	Kota Mataram	452	183	269	59,51
3	Kabupaten Lombok Barat	1.755	369	1.386	78,97
4	Kabupaten Lombok Tengah	1.915	606	1.309	68,36
5	Kabupaten Lombok Utara	648	218	430	66,36
6	Kabupaten Lombok Timur	1.736	744	992	57,14
7	Kabupaten Sumbawa Barat	776	480	296	38,14
8	Kabupaten Sumbawa	2.195	1.035	1.160	52,85
9	Kabupaten Dompu	1.053	620	433	41,12
10	Kabupaten Bima	938	436	502	53,52
11	Kota Bima	660	273	387	58,64
	Jumlah	12.146	4.980	7.166	53,25

Source: statistic.atrbpn.go.id

The table above shows the significant achievement of employee performance towards the settlement of arrears that can be completed by each work unit within the BPN Regional Office of West Nusa Tenggara Province. In terms of work, each employee has an individual responsibility, so each employee is required to be able to carry out work in accordance with standards, operations, and procedures (SOP).

The increased performance achievement shown by the West Nusa Tenggara Provincial BPN Regional Office Employees in resolving service arrears is because the Ministry of ATR / BPN 2019 has gradually implemented services to the public digitally, including by issuing PERMEN ATR / BPN Number 9 of 2019 concerning Electronic Mortgage Rights. To support digital services, the Ministry of ATR / BPN has established a digital transformation roadmap from 2019 to 2024. In 2022 the Ministry of ATR / BPN has implemented electronic services in 7 (seven) land services, including SK Registration, Checking, Roya, Transfer, Mortgage Rights, SKPT, and Change of Rights.

The application of electronic services carried out by the National Land Agency is called the web-based Land Office Computerization Program (KKP) which is intended to facilitate service activities. Land Office Computerization (KKP) is an integrated computerization system activity in the ranks of the National Land Agency of the Republic of Indonesia in order to improve the standardization of land services. The purpose of the Land Office Computerization System (KKP) is to ensure the use of land information for stakeholders (apparatus) of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, monitoring services, and printing all List of Contents (DI) reports. The form of application of reporting data and information dissemination for internal and external purposes is entered into the computer gradually and the data enters the data processing of the Land Office Computerized System to be processed.

The achievement of employee performance is indeed influenced by many variables, both variables originating from within the employee himself and from variables outside the employee himself (de Waal, 2018). The results of research conducted by Fatmah (2020) and Mwita & Jonathan (2019) state that the factors that influence performance are information technology and digital transformation. The indicators that affect employee performance are as follows: quantity, quality, efficiency, discipline, initiative, thoroughness, leadership, and creativity (Afandi, 2018).

Information technology is a science that studies the design, development, implementation, management of computer-based information systems, especially software and hardware applications. (Rachmawati, 2014). According to Rachmawati (2014) information technology indicators are as follows: computer hardware (hardware), and computer software (software).

Information technology is shown to have a favorable and significant impact on employee performance based on the findings of prior study by Kertahadi, et al. (2016). Information technology utilized by businesses has a considerable favorable

impact on the performance of employees, according to other study findings by other researchers (such as Resfiana, 2019; Rachman, 2020; Adnalim, 2019; and Hamid, 2016). The usage of information technology does not significantly affect employee performance, according to studies by Oktari (2010) and Ardianto (2014). Nevertheless, Amalia's (2010) study's findings indicate that the impact of information technology on worker performance is both favorable and negligible.

Digital transformation is a further component that influences worker performance (Mwita & Joanthan, 2019). According to Augustian et al. (2019), digital transformation is a process that involves integrating all of the organization's system components using digital technologies such as cloud computing, mobile computing, and virtualization. Indicators of digital transformation, according to Matt et al. (2015), include customer experience, product innovation, strategy, organization, process digitization, collaboration, information technology, culture & expertise, and transformation management.

The findings of a study done in 2016 by Nwankpa & Roumani showed that digital transformation helps to increase employee performance. The findings of studies conducted by Henfridsson et al. (2018) and Nambisan et al. (2017) demonstrate a favorable and substantial correlation between digital transformation and employee performance. According to Karagiannaki et al. (2017), digital transformation is also a key element that determines whether a firm will survive and how well its employees perform. However, the findings of studies by Brynjolfsson & Hitt (2000), and Mithas et al. (2005) indicate that there is no meaningful connection between digital transformation and employee performance. Because of the implications of digital transformation, which demonstrate that it is not the only approach to enhance employee performance, the findings of Aral & Weill's (2007) study also demonstrate that there is no substantial association between digital transformation and employee performance.

Job happiness is another element that might influence excellent or poor employee performance. A person's sentiments regarding his or her employment, workplace, and connections with coworkers are expressed in the form of job satisfaction. An employee should be able to engage with their work environment and feel satisfied in their position for the task to be done effectively and in line with corporate objectives (Antasari et al, 2015). According to Dewi et al. (2014), work satisfaction is more than just a sensation of like (satisfied) or disliking (dissatisfied) in one's employment. Instead, job satisfaction is a development of how a person feels about his or her job and several indications of that job.

Job satisfaction has been linked to improved employee performance, according to a number of researches (Dewi et al., 2014; Rosita, 2016; Cahyana & Jati, 2016; Rosita & Yuniati, 2016; Hanafi & Yohana, 2017; Nurnaningsih & Wahyono, 2017; Fadhil & Mayowan, 2018). Imelda (2019) claims that while work satisfaction partially has no substantial impact on employee performance, concurrently, motivation, advancement, and satisfaction all have a big impact. This is corroborated by Purba et al. (2019), who claim that while

work happiness, motivation, and discipline all concurrently have a favorable impact on employee performance, job satisfaction itself has a limited impact.

According to a number of research findings, using information technology significantly and favorably affects job satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2019; Hanafi and Yohana, 2017; Melinda, 2013; Rofano, 2019). Nilnannah (2014) made a contrary claim, claiming that the adoption of information technology did not significantly affect work satisfaction. On the other hand, a number of studies (such as Suratini et al., 2015; Oktari, 2010; Muzakki et al., 2016; Nugroho, 2016; Refano et al., 2019) demonstrate the effects of information technology use on individual performance via the lens of work satisfaction. While this is going on, Mellinda's research from 2017 shows that job satisfaction cannot mediate the relationship between technology use and individual performance. This is because some jobs, like those involving decision-making, learning, correspondence, signing documents, teaching, and laboratories, are more manual in nature and not always directly related to the use of information technology.

According to Hasibuan's research, work happiness can moderate the impact of information technology efficacy on employee performance (2019). Additionally, previous studies have shown that the impact of information technology on employee performance can be mitigated by work satisfaction (Prasetyo & Marlina, 2019; Nabawi, 2019). The findings of studies by Rosmaini & Tanjung (2019) and Adhan et al. (2020), on the other hand, show that work satisfaction has the power to mediate the impact of digital transformation on employee performance. However, work happiness is unable to moderate the impact of information technology use on individual performance, according to Antasari & Yuniartha's (2015) research.

Due to a study gap on the impact of information technology and digital transformation on employee performance, it is crucial to reexamine this relationship by include a mediating element, namely work satisfaction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Employee Performance*

Performance is derived etymologically from the term performance. According to Mariyani (2016), performance refers to the quality and quantity of work completed by an employee while carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him. Performance can also refer to a person's actual achievement in their work. Mukhlisoh (2016), on the other hand, presented a different viewpoint, arguing that performance refers to the implementation of a task and its successful completion in line with its obligations in order to provide the desired outcomes. According to Magnier-Watanabe et al. (2020), the execution of tasks and activities is what determines how well an employee performs. According to Magnier-Watanabe et al. (2000) and Costa et al. (2019), organizational success is also influenced by employee performance. Employee performance is a crucial factor in enhancing business performance (Edgar et al., 2018).

➤ *Information Technology*

In order to handle and disseminate information of both a financial and non-financial character, information technology is separated into two technologies: computer technology and communication technology (Adnalin, 2019). The planning, creating, implementing, maintaining, or administering of information systems utilizing computers, particularly software and hardware, is referred to as information technology, according to the Information Technology Association of America (ITAA). In order to securely change, store, protect, process, communicate, and obtain information, electronic computers and computer software are used (Alamsyah et al., 2020). Information technology combines computer technology with communication technology, with computer technology consisting of hardware and software that processes and stores information and communication technology acting as a means of information transmission. According to Amalia and Rohman (2020), information technology is a collection of technologies with the ability to produce, store, modify, and utilise information in any form.

➤ *Digital Transformation*

Digital transformation is the process of integrating all system components inside the company by using digital technology such as cloud computing, mobile computing, and virtualization technologies. According to Watsono and Furinto (2018), the term "digital transformation" can also refer to a process that combines business and technological innovation and results in alterations to an organization's internal and external environment in terms of its ecosystem, value, process, position, and structure. Organizations and society are becoming increasingly reliant on data and technology, necessitating the need for digital transformation to help enterprises grow (Yopan et al., 2022). As a result, digital transformation is anticipated to boost operational efficiency and add value for customers. According to Nadkarni & Prugl (2021), digital transformation is the application of technology to enhance a company's overall performance or market reach. Vassilakopoulou & Hustad (2021) provide a different definition of digital transformation, stating that it is the third and greatest level of digital abilities attained when the use of technology also fosters innovation and creativity and propels substantial changes in professional or knowledge sectors. The changes brought by or affected by the use of digital technologies in the workplace is another broad definition of digital transformation.

➤ *Job Satisfaction*

A person's sentiments regarding his or her employment, workplace, and connections with coworkers are expressed in the form of job satisfaction. An employee should be able to engage with their work environment and feel satisfied in their position for the task to be completed effectively and in line with corporate objectives (Antasari et al., 2015). According to Dewi et al. (2014), work satisfaction is more than just a sense of like (satisfied) or disliking (dissatisfied) with one's employment. Instead, job satisfaction is a development of how a person feels about his or her job and several indications of that job. As for how employees feel about their work, Rosita and Yuniati (2016) claim that job satisfaction is a positive or negative emotional state. Job satisfaction is a reflection of

how someone feels about their work. A person's sentiments about his or her employment are what Fadhil & Mayowan (2018) describe as job satisfaction. According to Imelda (2019), job satisfaction is the efficiency or emotional reaction to a variety of employment metrics. Hanafi and Yohana (2017) assert that job satisfaction is a favorable emotional state resulting from an assessment of one's work experience. General measures of job happiness include income, recognition, the connection between employees and supervisors, and satisfaction with the job itself.

➤ *The Effect of Information Technology on Employee Performance*

The company's computer facilities have a big impact on how information technology is used there. More user-supporting amenities will make it simpler for users to get the information they need to finish particular jobs within the firm. The goal of using information technology in a business is to increase performance and output from the human resources who utilize the system. Information technology has a favorable impact on employee activities or activities related to the execution of their jobs, which helps employees perform better across nearly all areas of the business, including marketing, personnel, and even top management. Information technology is one of the variables influencing performance in this situation. With all the advantages and value additions that come from using technology, it may enhance business performance, employee/employee productivity, quality, efficiency, innovation, and customer response. Adnalin (2019), Resfiana (2019), Rachman (2020), Hamid (2016), and other researchers have found that the usage of information technology by businesses significantly improves employee performance. Information technology has a favorable and negligible impact on employee performance, according to Amalia's (2010) research. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H1: Information technology has a significant positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *The Effect of Digital Transformation on Employee Performance*

A person's performance is the outcome they obtain while carrying out the responsibilities that have been given to them. Employee performance is influenced by a variety of factors, including abilities and expertise, job knowledge, work design, personality or character, motivation, leadership or behavior of a leader, leadership style or attitude of a leader, organizational culture, work environment, loyalty, and work discipline. Employee performance is influenced by corporate culture, according to the elements that have been discussed (Agustian et al., 2019). Digital transformation is thought to present a number of managerial issues, according to prior research. Business process restructuring, system design modifications, framing challenges, and partner interactions can all result from the adoption of digital technology (Abrell et al., 2016). Nwankpa & Roumani's (2016) research found that digital transformation contributes to bettering employee performance. Organizations need to understand how crucial digital transformation is to raising worker productivity.

Employee performance and digital transformation have a favorable and substantial association, according to studies by Henfridsson et al. (2018) and Nambisan et al. (2017). According to the findings of Karagiannaki et al. (2017), digital transformation is a crucial element that determines whether a firm will survive and how well its employees perform. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be compiled:

- *H2: Digital transformation has a significant positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *The Effect of Information Technology on Job Satisfaction*

It is currently impossible to separate the existence of information technology from its function in the execution of employee activities. Employees who comprehend and are proficient in using information technology apps will benefit from them since they will be able to accomplish their task more quickly while also improving the quality of their work (Kertahadi et al., 2016). By removing their constraints, the use of information technology will assist employees in carrying out their duties. One thing that is crucial to achieving the best work results in a firm is employee job happiness. Naturally, a person who is happy in his or her profession would give it his or her best to do the tasks assigned to him or her. Employee productivity and job outcomes will so improve to their full potential. Public accounting firm auditors will always deal with elements that are anticipated to have an impact on job happiness, thus they must always strive to attain the highest degree of job satisfaction in each audit activity. Conflict between job and family is one of these issues (Resfiana, 2019). At all organizational levels, information technology is used to describe business operations. Information technology is utilized at the operational level to boost employee happiness. The degree of ease, such as how simple it is to use and understand, how clear and adaptable it is, and how easy it is to operate, affects how people utilize information technology. Employee performance and work satisfaction will increase if they perceive that information technology and digital transformation have considerably benefited them. Job satisfaction is a favorable attitude about one's work that comes from evaluating its qualities. According to Hasibuan's research, using information technology significantly and favorably affects job satisfaction. Hanafi and Yohana (2017), Melinda (2013), and Rofano (2019) all provide support to this. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H3: Information technology has a significant positive effect on the job satisfaction on employees of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *The Effect of Digital Transformation on Job Satisfaction*

Employees' emotional attitudes towards their jobs are created via evaluations of many parts of their employment. The ability to exert effort, the attainment of outcomes for the work completed, and what the organization can offer in relation to the work and the consequences of the work are all aspects of the job (Hasibuan, 2019). Technology in an

organization, according to Refano et al. (2019), includes both labor practices and equipment. In theory, technology should make it easier for everybody to do their jobs, including workers. The usage of technology by employees in the course of their job will not be segregated. The speed and precision of labor will grow thanks to modern technology, but there are drawbacks as well. Job satisfaction will decline with less difficult tasks. Not to mention that workers will presume that technology utilization will be a major factor in how well their work turns out. This indicates that their success is backed by cutting-edge technology rather than being the result of their best efforts. Nwankpa & Roumani's (2016) research found that digital transformation contributes to bettering employee performance. Organizations need to understand how crucial digital transformation is to raising worker productivity. The findings of studies by Rosmaini & Tanjung (2019) and Adhan et al. (2020) demonstrate that the digital transformation has a considerable impact on work satisfaction. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H4: Digital transformation has a significant positive effect on the job satisfaction on employees of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance*

Job happiness is one of the factors that might influence employee performance. Employee performance can be categorized as either high or bad depending on job satisfaction. Employee performance is anticipated to increase as job satisfaction levels rise, enabling the organization to meet its objectives for outstanding work outcomes and high production. Employees that experience high levels of satisfaction are more productive than those who do not, hence unsatisfied employees will perform poorly (Rosmaini & Tanjung, 2019). According to Hanafi and Yohana (2017), employee self-actualization depends greatly on work satisfaction. A worker who is unsatisfied at work will never mature psychologically and will ultimately grow irritated. Job satisfaction has been shown to significantly improve employee performance, according to studies by Dewi et al. (2014), Rosita (2016), Cahyana & Jati (2016), Rosita and Yuniati (2016), Hanafi & Yohana (2017), Nurnaningsih & Wahyono (2017), and Fadhil & Mayowan (2018). Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H5: Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *Job Satisfaction Mediates the Relationship between Information Technology and Employee Performance*

A person's attitude toward their employment is defined as job satisfaction. It is the effect of how they view their work and how well they fit within the business. In essence, a person's level of pleasure will depend on the value system that is applicable to him. This is a result of individual variances. The greater the degree of happiness felt, and vice versa, the more features of the work that fit the individual's preferences. Information technology is meant to address issues, encourage creativity, and improve user effectiveness

and efficiency. Even while information technology is capable of doing extremely complex tasks and can even speed up human labor, it will not operate well if human capacity to use it is not supported. According to research, work satisfaction may operate as a mediating factor between the use of information technology and employee performance, with the degree of job happiness influencing how the use of information technology affects employee performance. The findings of Hasibuan's research (2019) demonstrate that work satisfaction has the capacity to moderate the impact of information technology effectiveness on employee performance. The findings of studies by Prasetyo & Marlina (2019) and Nabawi (2019) further demonstrate that job satisfaction can operate as a mediator between information technology's effect on employee performance and work satisfaction. However, according to Antasari & Yuniartha (2015), work happiness cannot mitigate the impact of information technology use on an individual's performance. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H6: Job satisfaction mediates the significant positive effect of information technology on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

➤ *Job Satisfaction Mediates the Relationship between Digital Transformation and Employee Performance*

According to Hasibuan (2019), a person's performance is impacted by both his ability and how much effort he puts forth. According to Robbins, a person's ability (A), motivation (M), and opportunity (O) elements have a significant impact on how well they do; in other words, performance is a function of ability, motivation, and opportunity. According to Lawyer, a person's performance is impacted by their effort, skill, and perceptions about their job. Theoretically, there are three kinds of factors that affect employee performance that may be improved: individual factors (abilities and skills), psychological factors, and organizational factors. Humans are still necessary for digital transformation since they are the ones who utilize it and technology is only a tool. Employee skill in using information technology is required for its utilization in the business. The capacity of employees to leverage digital transformation may be minimal, which may have an impact on how well they do their jobs. such that it will have an impact on how these people perform. According to Rosmaini & Tanjung's and Adhan et al.'s (2019) and Rosmaini & Tanjung's (2020) studies, work satisfaction can mitigate the impact of digital transformation on employee performance. Based on the description above, this hypothesis can be prepared:

- *H7: Job satisfaction mediates the significant positive effect of digital transformation on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province.*

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Utilizing quantitative research techniques, this investigation. This research falls within the category of associative research in terms of the level of explanation. Causal linkages, symmetrical relationships, and interactive or reciprocal relationships are all parts of associative study. According to Siregar (2013) in Jamaluddin 2020, research with a causal link aims to understand the connection between two or more variables. Information was gathered from respondents in this study utilizing the survey technique of data gathering. The questionnaire technique, according to Ghozali

(2013), is a way of gathering data that entails a sequence of inquiries meant to elicit information from respondents. Civil Servants (PNS) in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of NTB Province made up the population used in this study, which totaled to 386 people. The number of samples was determined using the Slovin method, and 197 employees employed a proportional random sampling procedure to collect the samples. Data were gathered via a survey on a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Smart PLS 3.2.7 was used to analyze the study's data using the Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM).

IV. RESULTS

➤ Path Coefficients

Fig 1 LS Path Coefficient Model Bootstrapping

Table 2 Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Influence between Variables	Original Sample	t-Statistics	P Values	
H1	X1 -> Y	-0.015	0.164	0.870	Not Proven
H2	X2 -> Y	0.271	2.483	0.013	Proven
H3	X1 -> Z	0.289	4.092	0.000	Proven
H4	X2 -> Z	0.445	5.982	0.000	Proven
H5	Z -> Y	0.479	5.452	0.000	Proven
H6	X1->Z -> Y	0.139	3.427	0.001	Proven
H7	X2-> Z -> Y	0.213	3.820	0.000	Proven

Sources: Research Data, 2023

➤ *Based on the Table above, the Relationship between Variables (Hypothesis Test Results) can be Explained as follows:*

- *Hypothesis Testing 1 (There is a Significant Effect of Information Technology on Employee Performance).*

The results of testing hypothesis 1 show a p-value of 0.870 greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no effect of information technology on employee performance, meaning that it is not in accordance with hypothesis 1 (hypothesis 1 is not proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 2 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of Digital Transformation on Employee Performance)*

The results of testing hypothesis 2 show that the p-value of 0.013 is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant effect on digital transformation on employee performance. So that it is in accordance with hypothesis 2 (hypothesis 2 is proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 3 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of Information Technology on job Satisfaction).*

The results of testing hypothesis 3 show a p-value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a positive effect of information technology on job satisfaction which is in accordance with hypothesis 3 (hypothesis 3 is proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 4 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of Digital Transformation on job Satisfaction).*

The results of testing hypothesis 4 show that the p-value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a positive effect of digital transformation on job satisfaction which is in accordance with hypothesis 4 (hypothesis 4 is proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 5 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of job Satisfaction on Employee Performance).*

The results of testing hypothesis 3 show that the p-value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a positive effect of job satisfaction on employee performance which is in accordance with hypothesis 5 (hypothesis 5 is proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 6 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of Job Satisfaction Mediating the Effect of Information Technology on Employee Performance).*

The results of testing hypothesis 3 show that the p-value of 0.001 is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of information technology on employee performance which is in accordance with hypothesis 6 (hypothesis 6 is proven).

- *Hypothesis Testing 7 (There is a Positive and Significant Effect of Job Satisfaction Mediating the Effect of Digital Transformation on Employee Performance).*

The results of testing hypothesis 3 show that the p-value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of digital

transformation on employee performance which is in accordance with hypothesis 7 (hypothesis 7 is proven).

➤ *R Square*

Table 3 R Square Results

Employee Performance (Y)	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	0.850	0.834

Sources: Research Data, 2023

The output result of the R-Square value of work enthusiasm is 0.850. These results indicate that the construct variables of information technology, digital transformation,7 and job satisfaction can explain the variability of employee performance constructs by 85%, while the remaining 15% is influenced by other factors that are not included in this research variable. From the results of the R-Square value of 85%, it is included in the strong category.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *The Effect of Information Technology on Employee Performance*

The results showed that information technology had no significant effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This can be interpreted that the existence of information technology cannot improve employee performance. The majority of respondents or employees in the land office are in the range of 31-40 years old and are included in the millennial generation. In line with research conducted by Wicaksana, S. A., Nurika, R., & Asrunputri, A. P. (2020) states that the millennial generation mostly has the habit of going home early and often not entering the office. The implementation of electronic land services requires work discipline from employees, especially for the application of information technology which has not been running for a long time so it requires perseverance from employees to adapt and adjust work that was originally done analogically to digital. The general impact of these habits will affect the decline in employee performance. In addition, it is suspected that it has no effect on the relationship between variables, namely in the form of computer facilities provided that are not really suitable for use to support performance optimization or improve employee performance so that they find it difficult to do various jobs quickly. In line with research conducted by Wijaksono, Sutapa & Fajariah (2022) states that facilities are also very important for employees to improve employee performance. Facilities as the main driver of employee needs to carry out activities so that work is easily completed. To improve employee performance, companies always try to provide work facilities needed by employees so that the spirit of work is even more active, especially in the form of adequate computer equipment in accordance with the latest updates or advances in the times equipped with various supporting features. The results of information technology research have no effect on the performance of employees of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, in line with the results of research conducted by Ardianto

(2014) that the use of information technology has no significant effect on employee performance.

➤ *The Effect of Digital Transformation on Employee Performance*

The results showed that Digital Transformation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This can be interpreted that the existence of digital transformation will improve employee performance. Conversely, if the lower the digital transformation implemented in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it will be followed by the lower employee performance. The findings in this study show that the majority of employees feel ready and always want to contribute to the digitization process of documents. In addition, the digital land service innovation launched by the Ministry of ATR / BPN is very helpful for employees, both superiors and subordinates, in providing services to the community. This can be seen in every stage of the land service process, starting from the application counter to the output in the form of certificates. All of these stages must be accompanied by uploading documents to the Land Office Computerization application (KKP). So that overall, both superiors and subordinates feel that their performance is increasing with the various transformations in the digital field carried out by the Ministry of ATR / BPN. The results of the study that digital transformation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province are in line with the research of Antasari & Sukartha, (2015). The results of this study found that Digital Transformation and the use of information technology have a considerable effect on employee performance.

➤ *The Effect of Digital Transformation on Employee Performance*

The results showed that information technology has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that if better information technology is implemented in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it will be followed by an increase in job satisfaction. Conversely, if the information technology is implemented within the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it is followed by the lower employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This can also be seen from respondents' opinions about job satisfaction in the "high" category, which means that respondents are directly helped by the existence of information technology which is supported by cooperation with coworkers. The results of information technology research have a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, in line with the results of research conducted by Hasibuan (2019), Hanafi and Yohana (2017), Melinda (2013) and Rofano (2019) that the use of information technology has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

➤ *The Effect of Digital Transformation on Job Satisfaction*

The results showed that digital transformation has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that if the better the digital transformation implemented in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province is followed by an increase in job satisfaction. Conversely, if the lower the digital transformation implemented within the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it is followed by the lower employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. Respondents' opinions about digital transformation and job satisfaction are both in the "good and high" category. This means that employees at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province have strong digital transformation capabilities to carry out tasks in order to serve the public in the land sector electronically supported by high job satisfaction. The results of information technology research have a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, in line with the results of research conducted by Rosmaini & Tanjung (2019) and Adhan et al. (2020) prove that there is a significant influence between digital transformation on job satisfaction.

➤ *The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance*

The results showed that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that higher job satisfaction will make an increase in employee performance. Vice versa, if the lower the job satisfaction will make the employee's performance decrease.

In the test, it can also be seen that respondents' opinions about job satisfaction are "high", meaning that employees have high/strong satisfaction in carrying out their duties at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province it affects employee performance. The coworker factor which is an indicator of job satisfaction has a "very high" category, which means that employees at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province in carrying out their duties are always carried out in collaboration with their coworkers. The results of job satisfaction research have a positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, in line with the results of research conducted by Dewi et al. (2014), Rosita (2016), Cahyana & jati (2016), Rosita and Yuniati (2016), Hanafi & Yohana (2017), Nurnaningsih & Wahyono (2017), Fadhil & Mayowan (2018), state that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

➤ *The Effect of Job Satisfaction Mediating Information Technology on Employee Performance*

The results showed that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of information technology on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. If information technology directly has no effect on employee performance, but when mediated

by job satisfaction, it becomes a significant positive effect. This can be interpreted that information technology can affect employee performance if it can maintain or increase employee job satisfaction. This is in line with the research of Prasetyo & Marlina (2019) and Nabawi (2019) that job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence between information technology on employee performance. So that researchers can conclude that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of information technology on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province as a whole (Full mediation) is starting with high job satisfaction with existing indicators. With the respondent's opinion that the salary given is sufficient and feasible, it causes comfort in working so that to meet the need for computer facilities that are still inadequate, employees are willing to bring personal computers. Through job satisfaction, information technology can improve employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province.

➤ *The Effect of Job Satisfaction Mediating Digital Transformation on Employee Performance*

The results showed that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of information technology on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. Digital transformation indirectly affects employee performance through job satisfaction. So that job satisfaction can appropriately become a mediating variable. Respondents's opinions about job satisfaction in the "high" category mean that employees have high job satisfaction with what they have received from the office where they work. In the test, it can also be seen that respondents' opinions about employee performance according to both superiors and staff are in the "very good" category, meaning that employees have high performance in carrying out their duties at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. With two variables where the respondent's opinion is "high" and "very good" so that it significantly affects employee performance through job satisfaction. Based on the results of hypothesis testing on indirect relationships, it is found that Job Satisfaction has a partial mediation role in the relationship between digital transformation and employee performance. These results found no change from the direct relationship, where digital transformation was found to have a positive effect on employee performance. So it can be seen that job satisfaction has a partial mediation role in the relationship between digital transformation and employee performance, where the presence or absence of job satisfaction, digital transformation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Job satisfaction can mediate the effect of digital transformation on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province in line with research by Rosmaini & Tanjung (2019), Adhan et al. (2020), proving that job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence between digital transformation on employee performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

➤ *From the Results of the Research and Discussion above, the Conclusions of the Research that can be Drawn are:*

- Information technology has no effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that the existence of information technology cannot improve the performance of these employees. This can also be seen from the respondents' opinions about information technology with hardware indicators where the computer facilities provided by the land office to support work are in the "good" category, which means that the land office has not maximized hardware support in the context of information technology so that it does not significantly affect employee performance.
- Digital transformation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that the higher the digital transformation will make increase in employee performance. It can also be seen from the respondents' opinions about digital transformation that all indicators have a "good" category and the most influential is that employees contribute to the digitization process of documents. This can be seen in every stage of the land service process, from the application counter to the output in the form of certificates. At all stages must be accompanied by uploading documents to the Land Office Computerization application.
- Information technology has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that if better information technology is implemented in the Land Office environment in West Nusa Tenggara Province, it is followed by an increase in job satisfaction. Conversely, if the information technology is implemented in the environment of the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it is followed by the lower employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This can also be seen from the respondents' opinions about job satisfaction in the "high" category, which means that respondents are directly helped by the existence of information technology which is supported by cooperation with coworkers.
- Digital transformation has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that if the better the digital transformation implemented in the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province is followed by an increase in job satisfaction. Conversely, if the lower the digital transformation is implemented within the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province, it is followed by the lower employee job satisfaction at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province.

- Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. This means that higher job satisfaction will make an increase in employee performance. Vice versa, if the lower the job satisfaction will make the employee's performance decrease. In the test it can also be seen that respondents' opinions about job satisfaction are "high", meaning that employees have high/strong satisfaction in carrying out their duties at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province so that it affects employee performance.
- Job satisfaction can mediate the effect of information technology on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. Respondents' opinions about information technology indicators regarding hardware facilities in the form of computers in the "good" category indicate that there are still uneven office facilities provided to employees so that they do not affect employee performance. However, it is different with respondents' opinions about job satisfaction "very high", meaning that employees have strong / high satisfaction in carrying out their work duties at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province so that it significantly affects employee performance. This employee opinion makes employee performance significant through job satisfaction.
- Job satisfaction can mediate the effect of digital transformation on employee performance at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. Respondents' opinions about job satisfaction in the "high" category mean that employees have high job satisfaction with what they have received from the office where they work. In the test, it can also be seen that respondents' opinions about employee performance according to both superiors and staff are in the "very good" category, meaning that employees have high performance in carrying out their duties at the Regional Office of the National Land Agency of West Nusa Tenggara Province. With two variables where the respondent's opinion is "high" and "very good" so that it significantly affects employee performance through job satisfaction.

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